

Excess molar volumes, viscosity deviations and isentropic compressibility changes in binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide with 2-methoxyethanol and water in the temperature range 298.15 to 318.15 K^ψ

Pitchai J. Victor^a, Debasish Das^b and Dilip K. Hazra^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, St. Joseph's College, Darjeeling-734 104, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, North Bengal University, Darjeeling-734 430, India

E-mail : dkhazra@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-353-2581546

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Densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities of the binary mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and + water have been measured at temperatures 298.15 ≤ T/K ≤ 318.15. The excess molar volumes, viscosity deviations and isentropic compressibility changes of the mixtures from the ideal mole fraction rule have been calculated from these data. The computed results have been fitted to the Redlich-Kister polynomial. The results have been interpreted in terms of structural effects of the solvents.

Thermodynamic excess properties of binary liquid mixtures have been very helpful to obtain information on the intermolecular interactions and geometrical effects in these systems^{1,2}. Solvents like 2-methoxyethanol (ME) and *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (DMA) find a wide range of applications of technological importance, namely, as solvents and solubilizing agents in organic synthesis, reaction kinetics and electrochemical studies³⁻⁶.

The amide group in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide is a good model of a peptide bond. A systematic study of the structural and energetic consequences of the interaction between *N,N*-dimethylacetamide and water will enable us to understand how water exercises thermodynamic and kinetic control over the chemical activities of polypeptides in aqueous media.

We have measured densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities for the liquid mixtures of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + water over the entire range of their compositions at temperatures 298.15 ≤ T/K ≤ 318.15. The excess molar volumes (V^E), viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) and isentropic compressibility changes ($\Delta\kappa_s$) of these systems have been calculated at three temperatures and the results are reported.

Results and discussion

The kinematic viscosity (ν) and the absolute viscosity

(η) are given by the following equations :

$$\nu = Ct - Kt \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = \nu\rho \quad (2)$$

where t is the efflux time, ρ is the density and C and K are the characteristic constants of the viscometer. The values of the constants C and K determined by using water and benzene were found to be $1.648 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^2$ and -0.02331 cm^2 respectively.

Isentropic compressibility (κ_s) has been calculated by the following formula :

$$\kappa_s = 1/(u^2\rho) \quad (3)$$

where u is the sound velocity and ρ is the density of the experimental liquid. The densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol mixture and *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + water mixture as a function of mole fraction of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The excess function have been evaluated using the following equations :

$$V^E = V - (V_1x_1 + V_2x_2) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - (\eta_1x_1 + \eta_2x_2) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta\kappa_s = \kappa_s - (\kappa_{s1}x_1 + \kappa_{s2}x_2) \quad (6)$$

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (u) of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol mixtures at different mole fractions (x) of DMA, at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K

x (DMA)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)			η (mPa.s)			u (m s ⁻¹)		
	298.15	308.15	318.15	298.15	308.15	318.15	298.15	308.15	318.15
0.0000	0.95979	0.95251	0.94623	1.543	1.257	1.050	1339.31	1303.85	1269.05
0.0301	0.95927	0.95221	0.94614	1.535	1.254	1.048	1344.60	1308.91	1273.95
0.0600	0.95875	0.95175	0.94583	1.528	1.250	1.046	1349.92	1314.07	1278.68
0.0871	0.95826	0.95132	0.94535	1.520	1.247	1.045	1354.65	1318.87	1283.23
0.1250	0.95756	0.95060	0.94450	1.507	1.239	1.041	1361.02	1325.37	1289.40
0.1767	0.95656	0.94951	0.94317	1.488	1.228	1.034	1369.15	1333.95	1297.74
0.2250	0.95556	0.94838	0.94186	1.466	1.214	1.026	1376.15	1341.51	1305.29
0.2902	0.95413	0.94677	0.94004	1.432	1.192	1.011	1385.07	1350.76	1314.63
0.3640	0.95241	0.94489	0.93797	1.390	1.164	0.991	1394.65	1360.30	1324.27
0.4602	0.95012	0.94239	0.93521	1.329	1.122	0.960	1406.55	1371.81	1335.76
0.5200	0.94866	0.94081	0.93347	1.289	1.092	0.938	1413.59	1378.50	1342.40
0.5611	0.94764	0.93972	0.93226	1.260	1.070	0.921	1418.27	1382.83	1346.66
0.6200	0.94616	0.93815	0.93050	1.216	1.038	0.897	1424.60	1388.66	1352.30
0.6654	0.94499	0.93694	0.92913	1.181	1.011	0.876	1429.13	1393.07	1356.32
0.7250	0.94347	0.93534	0.92728	1.135	0.977	0.849	1434.83	1398.76	1361.49
0.7732	0.94225	0.93406	0.92576	1.099	0.949	0.827	1439.49	1403.31	1365.63
0.8250	0.94094	0.93264	0.92413	1.059	0.919	0.803	1444.16	1408.11	1369.92
0.8847	0.93945	0.93101	0.92224	1.014	0.885	0.775	1449.22	1413.49	1374.74
0.9501	0.93787	0.92918	0.92011	0.965	0.847	0.746	1454.89	1419.33	1380.09
1.0000	0.93669	0.92776	0.91849	0.927	0.819	0.723	1459.18	1423.75	1384.11

Table 2. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (u) of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + water mixtures at different mole fractions (x) of DMA at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K

x (DMA)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)			η (mPa.s)			u (m s ⁻¹)		
	298.15	308.15	318.15	298.15	308.15	318.15	298.15	308.15	318.15
0.0000	0.99709	0.99411	0.99026	0.889	0.721	0.600	1497.16	1519.35	1535.49
0.0250	0.99754	0.99377	0.98850	1.265	0.667	0.784	1566.07	1589.74	1584.83
0.0650	0.99854	0.99376	0.98714	1.871	1.428	1.106	1650.72	1652.48	1641.76
0.1011	0.99942	0.99275	0.98562	2.413	1.810	1.387	1702.24	1685.26	1664.61
0.1200	0.99981	0.99228	0.98495	2.754	2.307	1.533	1732.84	1696.17	1671.75
0.1495	0.99938	0.99170	0.98405	3.161	2.307	1.718	1732.84	1704.88	1675.75
0.2004	0.99820	0.98991	0.98155	3.728	2.661	1.944	1740.25	1706.21	1671.72
0.2512	0.99542	0.98722	0.97826	3.940	2.790	2.050	1735.61	1695.32	1657.44
0.3002	0.99130	0.98301	0.97405	3.941	2.784	2.056	1722.59	1678.70	1637.94
0.3501	0.98665	0.97830	0.96925	3.692	2.667	1.986	1700.48	1655.93	1613.90
0.4009	0.98192	0.97337	0.96433	3.341	2.474	1.853	1672.08	1631.39	1590.24
0.5018	0.97271	0.96379	0.95493	2.606	1.929	1.553	1619.80	1582.81	1540.91
0.6031	0.96380	0.95486	0.94606	1.995	1.568	1.274	1577.93	1539.75	1497.25
0.6505	0.95977	0.95094	0.94207	1.777	1.424	1.178	1560.65	1522.46	1480.39
0.7005	0.95589	0.94706	0.93822	1.592	1.305	1.085	1543.71	1505.54	1464.59
0.7550	0.95184	0.94310	0.93416	1.419	1.183	0.999	1525.94	1488.73	1447.76
0.8048	0.94838	0.93963	0.93072	1.284	1.085	0.932	1510.83	1472.92	1433.31
0.8501	0.94545	0.93661	0.92779	1.185	1.003	0.868	1497.74	1460.26	1421.06
0.9049	0.94192	0.93313	0.92421	1.083	0.922	0.803	1483.33	1445.84	1407.41
1.0000	0.93652	0.92771	0.91877	0.933	0.816	0.721	1461.90	1423.71	1385.17

where V , η and κ_s are the respective solution properties, and V_1 and V_2 , η_1 and η_2 , and κ_{s1} and κ_{s2} are the molar volumes, the coefficients of viscosities and the isentropic compressibilities of the pure components.

Graphical representations of V^E , $\Delta\eta$ and $\Delta\kappa_s$ as functions of mole fractions (x_1) of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide are given in Figs. 1 to 3.

Fig. 1. Variation of V^E of the binary mixtures of (a) *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (1) + 2-methoxyethanol (2) and *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (1) + water (2) at 298.15 K (O), 308.15 K (□) and 318.15 K (Δ).

The excess properties Y^E were fitted to the Redlich-Kister equation⁷,

$$Y^E = x_1(1 - x_1) \sum A_j(1 - 2x_1)^j \quad (7)$$

where Y^E is $V^E/(\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$ or $\Delta\eta/(\text{mPa.s})$ or $\Delta\kappa_s/(\text{bar}^{-1})$, and A_0 , A_1 , A_2 etc. are adjustable parameters. These parameters were evaluated by fitting $Y^E/x_1(1 - x_1)$ to eq. (7) by the method of least squares. The values of these parameters along with the standard deviation $\sigma(Y^E)$ of Y^E as defined by the equation,

$$\sigma(Y^E) = [\sum(Y^E_{\text{observed}} - Y^E_{\text{calculated}})^2 / (N - M)]^{0.5} \quad (8)$$

are recorded in Tables 3 and 4 for DMA + ME and DMA +

Fig. 2. Variation of $\Delta\eta$ of the binary mixtures of (a) *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (1) + 2-methoxyethanol (2) and (b) *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (1) + water (2) at 298.15 K (O), 308.15 K (□) and 318.15 K (Δ).

water systems respectively. In eq. (8), N is the total number of experimental points and M is the number of parameters.

Fig. 1 shows that both the systems *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol and *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + water have negative V^E values over the entire range of mole fraction and over the entire range of temperatures studied. Again for both of them there is a clear minima at a mole fraction of about 0.40 of DMA.

N,N-Dimethylacetamide is a dipolar aprotic solvent having dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 37.78$ at 298.15 K)⁸ and is moderately structured. On the other hand intermolecular hydrogen bonding exists in 2-methoxyethanol molecules in the liquid state^{3,9}. Moreover, the values of the Kirkwood correlation factors, g_k , for pure ME in the temperature range studied are not much greater than unity. This indicates that 2-methoxyethanol is a relatively unstructured liquid and that there are strong but not specific dipole-dipole forces exist in this solvent.

Consistent with some recent studies in amide + water mixtures¹⁰, we see that in DMA + water mixture the excess molar volumes at higher temperature are negative over the

Fig. 3. Variation of $\Delta\kappa_s$ of the binary mixtures of (a) *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (1) + 2-methoxyethanol (2) and (b) *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (1) + water (2) at 298.15 K (O), 308.15 K (□) and 318.15 K (Δ).

whole range of composition (Fig. 1). The magnitude of V^E slightly decreases with temperature. It must be pointed out here that the mixing of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide with water is a highly exothermic process.

The negative V^E values at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K and the clear minima in the curves indicate association through multiple hydrogen bonding between the polar group

of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide and water, although the pure liquids are presumed to be structured. Compared to the V^E values of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol, the V^E values here are five times more negative which may be a sign of strong solvation by hydrogen bonding accompanied by a minor destruction of water structure besides the possible interstitial accommodation of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide molecules inside the water cavities. In aqueous mixtures, the magnitude of V^E values reflects the strength of the hydrogen bonding between the polar groups of the amides and water. Due to the presence of the third methyl group in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide, the molecule becomes more polar than DMF, thereby increasing its hydrogen bonding ability and thus giving a more negative V^E in the *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + water mixture than in the DMF + water mixture¹¹.

Further, from Fig. 1 we see that, as the temperature rises there is a slight decrease in V^E in the water-rich portion. A rise in temperature leads to the breaking of the less dense hydrogen bonded structures and/or breakdown of self-associated *N,N*-dimethylacetamide aggregates, resulting in denser packing of molecules than before. It may also be accompanied by the release of free water and an increase in the fraction of unbounded molecules. This is consistent with the view that the excess molar volumes of aqueous mixtures reflect the structural changes of water introduced by the non-aqueous molecules¹¹.

All this suggests that the hydrogen bonding between water and *N,N*-dimethylacetamide is stronger and more compact than that between water molecules themselves, and hence the interaction between these unlike molecules gives a negative contribution to the V^E values.

From Fig. 2 it is observed that both DMA + ME and DMA + water systems show positive deviation of $\Delta\eta$ from ideality over the entire mole fraction range and over the

Table 3. Coefficients of least square fit by eq. (8) for excess molar volumes, viscosity deviations and isentropic compressibility changes of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol mixtures at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K

Property	Temp. (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	$\sigma(V^E)$
$V^E/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	298.15	-0.6672	0.2748	0.0155	-0.0237	0.0458	0.001
	308.15	-0.8147	0.2460	-0.2749	0.2092	-0.1750	0.001
	318.15	-1.0667	0.0977	-0.1514	0.8689	-0.7636	0.003
$\Delta\eta/\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$	298.15	0.2683	-0.1674	0.0054	0.0457	-0.0103	0.001
	308.15	0.2563	-0.1375	-0.0329	0.0277	0.0770	0.001
	318.15	0.2366	-0.1135	-0.0321	0.0321	0.0068	0.001
$\Delta\kappa_s/\text{Pa}^{-1}$	298.15	-0.4824	0.1631	-0.1264	0.0172	0.1370	0.002
	308.15	-0.5499	0.2881	-0.1114	-0.1326	0.1586	0.001
	318.15	-0.6518	0.2322	0.0729	-0.0523	-0.0275	0.001

Table 4. Coefficients of least square fit by eq. (8) for excess molar volumes, viscosity deviations and isentropic compressibility changes of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + water mixtures at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K

Property	Temp. (K)	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	σ (γ^E)
$V^E/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	298.15	-6.0140	2.5359	-0.8871	-1.5370	2.1658	0.009
	308.15	-5.9784	2.3413	-0.1007	-1.4837	1.1110	0.011
	318.15	-5.8716	2.1625	-0.3684	-1.5317	1.6935	0.007
$\Delta\eta/\text{mPa.s}$	298.15	7.0443	-15.3472	12.1404	8.5762	-12.6279	0.035
	308.15	4.9385	-9.9039	8.0347	4.8343	-8.0417	0.028
	318.15	3.5502	-6.6516	6.0496	3.0762	-6.4072	0.011
$\Delta\kappa_s/\text{Pa}^{-1}$	298.15	-3.4297	3.7710	-2.3595	4.2384	-4.3034	0.022
	308.15	-2.8559	3.2534	-1.8254	3.5934	-4.0838	0.019
	318.15	-2.3793	2.8886	-1.4153	2.8869	-3.6520	0.018

whole range of studied temperatures. In DMA + ME system the maxima correspond to a mole fraction of about 0.36 in DMA whereas in DMA + water the maxima occur at a mole fraction of about 0.30 in DMA.

The positive deviation indicates the predominance of specific hydrogen bonding interactions between the unlike molecules over the dissociation effects in both the systems. However, compared to DMA + ME system, $\Delta\eta_{\text{max}}$ in DMA + water is about 20 to 40 times larger, indicating very strong specific hydrogen bond interactions between *N,N*-dimethylacetamide and water molecules. Even a plot of η versus the mole fraction of DMA shows a large maximum suggesting high association or complex formation between water and the peptide dipole in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide. There are no such maxima in the other system.

As the temperature increases the magnitude of the viscosity deviation decreases only slightly in the case of the DMA + ME mixture, whereas in DMA + water the decrease is rather rapid. The sharp decrease may be due to the more rapid breaking up of the extensive hydrogen bonds in the latter than in the former.

The results of deviations in isentropic compressibility versus mole fraction at three different temperatures are given in Fig. 3.

For both the systems, the values of $\Delta\kappa_s$ are negative over the entire composition range and at all the three temperatures investigated. Negative $\Delta\kappa_s$ means that the mixture is less compressible than the corresponding ideal mixture suggesting a predominant hydrogen bond interaction between *N,N*-dimethylacetamide and water, thereby causing an increase in the ultrasonic velocity and a decrease in the compressibility of these solutions. This process continues until the mole fraction reaches around 0.20 in DMA at the three temperatures studied, because at this composition water cavities are filled up by interstitial solvation, or due to the

formation of hydrophobic *N,N*-dimethylacetamide aggregates, or as a consequence of both. It is thus apparent that the interstitial accommodation of DMA into water multimer structure becomes more effective and the positive contribution from the breaking of hydrogen bonds becomes less predominant, giving negative $\Delta\kappa_s$ values over the entire mole fraction range for these mixtures.

It is very interesting to note the variation of ultrasonic velocity with the mole fraction of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide in the DMA + water mixture. The ultrasonic velocities at the three temperatures converge at a particular mole fraction (around 0.065 in DMA) and then diverge in a reverse manner, after passing through maxima. A very similar trend is observed when κ_s is plotted against the mole fraction of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide in the same mixture, the transition taking place at the mole fraction of about 0.05 in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide, after which the curves diverge in the reverse manner and pass through minima and then increase (Fig. 3).

This phenomenon can be explained as follows. On increasing the amount of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide, the number of free water molecules around the *N,N*-dimethylacetamide molecules decrease gradually until a situation is reached where all the free water molecules are involved in the solvation. Such a condition may be correlated to the primary solvation (or hydration) of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide since the water molecules are not further compressed. At this condition, which is the convergence point in the above figure, κ_s becomes $\kappa_{s,h}^{12,13}$. The magnitude of this value for each system should indicate the level of interaction between the two components. The smaller the $\kappa_{s,h}$ value for a system in comparison to free water, the stronger will be the interaction. However, here, along with the process of solvation, interstitial accommodation of *N,N*-dimethylacetamide inside the water cavities may be taking place

simultaneously, along with a possible rupture of water structure. So the $\kappa_{s,h}$ obtained in this manner is only a qualitative indicator of the interaction.

Considering the experimental data of the two systems, it is apparent that, in the *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + water system strong hetero-association may be present through multiple hydrogen bonding between the polar groups of the amide and water. Large negative V^E and $\Delta\kappa_s$ values and large positive $\Delta\eta$ values are indicators for this phenomenon. On the other hand, there is a weak interaction and solvent structure effect in the *N,N*-dimethylacetamide + 2-methoxyethanol mixture, very akin to that in the *N,N*-dimethylacetamide and acetonitrile system¹⁴.

Experimental

N,N-Dimethylacetamide (E. Merck, India) was shaken well with charged CaO (A.R., B.D.H.) for 1–2 h, decanted, and distilled twice. The middle fraction was collected and used. Its density ($0.93669 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) and viscosity (0.9271 mPa.s) at 298.15 K, compared well with the literature values⁸ which are 0.9366 g cm^{-3} and 0.919 mPa.s , respectively.

2-Methoxyethanol (G.R., E. Merck) was dried with potassium carbonate and distilled twice in an all glass distillation set immediately before use and the middle fraction collected. The purified solvent had a density of $0.96002 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and a co-efficient of viscosity of 1.5414 mPa.s at 298.15 K. These values are in good agreement with the literature values⁹, which are $0.96028 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and 1.543 mPa.s respectively.

Densities were measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of 25 cm^3 and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 1 mm. The pycnometer was calibrated at (298.15, 308.15 and 318.15) K with triply distilled water and benzene. The reproducibility of the density measurements was $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. The temperature of the thermostatic water bath was controlled to $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$ of the desired temperature.

The kinematic viscosities were measured by means of a suspended-level Ubbelohde viscometer with a flow time of about 539 s for distilled water at 298.15 K. The time of

efflux was measured with a stopwatch capable of recording $\pm 0.1 \text{ s}$. The viscometer was always kept in a vertical position in a water thermostat controlled to $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$. The estimated error of the viscosity measurements was $\pm 0.2\%$.

Sound velocities were measured with an uncertainty of $\pm 0.3\%$, using a single-crystal variable-path ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) operating at 4 MHz, which was calibrated with water, methanol and benzene at each temperature. The temperature stability was maintained within $\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$ by circulating thermostated water around the cell by a circulating pump.

In all cases, the experiments were performed at least in five replicates for each composition and at each temperature and the results were averaged.

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